

Investigation of Aerodynamic and Aeroacoustic Performance of Various Distributed Electric Propulsion Configurations

Fang Han*, Luis Fernando Lopes De Moraes Filho[†], Djamel Rezgui[‡], Burak Buda Turhan[§], Mahdi Azarpeyvand[¶] and Abhishek Gautam**

Faculty of Engineering, University of Bristol, Queen's Building, University Walk, Bristol. BS8 1TR, United Kingdom.

Bin Zang^{††}

School of Engineering and Material Science, Queen Mary University of London, Mile End Road, Bethnal Green, London. E1 4NS, United Kingdom.

Beckett Y. Zhou^{‡‡}

Daniel Guggenheim School of Aerospace Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology, 270 Ferst Dr, Atlanta. GA 30332, United States.

This study aims to experimentally and numerically investigate and compare the aerodynamic and aeroacoustic characteristics of four leading-edge mounted Distributed Electric Propulsion (DEP) configurations under different angles of attack. The aerodynamic performance of individual propeller positions and wings is studied and compared experimentally. Numerical simulations using Vortex Particle Method (VPM) are performed to compare with the experimental results and provide aeroacoustic analysis of different configurations. The test rigs are designed and tested in the Wind Tunnel Laboratory at the University of Bristol. The baseline configuration is set as the 12-12-12 propeller DEP with three identical 12-inch propellers. The 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 configurations replace the outboard and inboard 12-inch propellers with a 15-inch propeller, respectively. The fourth 12-12 configuration includes only two 12-inch propellers mounted at the leading edge of the same wing. The thrust of all configurations is matched to be the same as the baseline configuration. The results indicate that for all three-propeller configurations, the mid propeller produces slightly less thrust than the other two propellers, and the higher the propeller rotational speeds and angles of attack, the larger the difference. The torque required to drive the 15-inch propellers is considerably higher than the 12-inch propellers. The efficiency of the 15-inch propeller is higher than that of the 12-inch propeller under most thrust settings. Wing performance comparisons show that the 12-12 configuration performs the worst among all configurations in wing lift-to-drag ratio at two different propeller rotational speeds. At lower propeller rotational speeds, the baseline configuration yields better lift-to-drag ratio of the wing, while the 12-12-15 configuration takes over at higher propeller rotational speeds. Numerical aerodynamic results illustrate good agreement on thrust predictions, whereas torque predictions can vary significantly with the propeller positions on the wing. Aeroacoustic simulations suggest the 12-12 configuration has around 7 dB higher noise emission than all three-propeller configurations for the 1st BPF, whereas only slight differences are observed between the three-propeller configurations.

* PhD Candidate, Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol

† PhD Candidate, Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol

‡ Associate Professor, Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, AIAA Member

§ Research Associate, Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, AIAA Member

¶ Professor of Aerodynamics and Aeroacoustics, Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, AIAA Member

** Research Associate, Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, AIAA Member

†† Senior Lecturer, School of Engineering and Material Science, Queen Mary University of London, AIAA Member

‡‡ Assistant Professor, Daniel Guggenheim School of Aerospace Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology, AIAA Senior Member

I. Nomenclature

α (<i>AoA</i>)	Angle of attack of the wing [°]	C_P	Coefficient of power [-]
α_L	Lamb's constant [-]	C_T and C_Q	Coefficients of thrust and torque [-]
γ	Vortex filament strength [m ² /s]	D	Diameter of propeller [m]
θ	Longitudinal plane observer angle [°]	J	Advance ratio [-]
φ	Propeller plane observer angle [°]	P	Propeller power [W]
σ	Particle smoothing length [m]	T and Q	Thrust and torque [N, Nm]
ν	Kinematic viscosity [m ² /s]	U_∞	Inflow speed [m/s]
Γ	Vortex particle strength [m ² /s]	V_x	Volume of particle [m ³]
Γ_p^{visc}	Vortex particle strength modified by viscous effects [m ² /s]		
∇	Gradient operator [-]	BPF	Blade Passage Frequency
η	Propeller efficiency [-]	DEP	Distributed Electric Propulsion
a_1	Squire's parameter [-]	ESC	Electronic speed control
n	Revolutions per second [s ⁻¹]	P/D	Pitch-to-diameter ratio
r_1, r_2	Vortex filament end points [m]	RPM	Revolution per minute
r_c	Vortex core radius [m]	SPL	Sound Pressure Level
u	Particle velocity [m/s]	VLM	Vortex Lattice Method
x	Particle position [m]	VPM	Vortex Particle Method
B	Blade number [-]	UAM	Urban Air Mobility
C_L and C_D	Coefficients of lift and drag [-]		

II. Introduction

The global aviation industry and experts are pursuing advanced, future-altering technology to lessen the environmental impact in recent years. Aero-propulsive coupled flow control technologies are recognised as potential solutions in improving aircraft performance, with several advanced concepts such as Distributed Electric Propulsion (DEP). These technologies demonstrate the capability of not only reducing fuel consumption and emissions in traditional aircraft but also playing a crucial role in the rapidly evolving field of Urban Air Mobility (UAM), where compact, highly efficient, and noise-conscious aircraft are essential for operating within city environments [1]. However, efficiently designing and validating these concepts create challenges for researchers, as these tasks tend to involve close cooperation between experimental and numerical works.

Previous works [2-7, 13-17] have already shown aerodynamic and aeroacoustic characteristics of various leading-edge mounted DEP concepts. de Vries et al. [2] conducted experiments on a series of arrangements of a three-propeller DEP system with different propeller “stagger positions” (distance from the propeller to the wing). They concluded that the performance of each propeller is strongly dependent on the spanwise and chordwise positions, with the middle propeller between the three in no stagger configuration being found to have around a 1.5% efficiency drop compared to isolated propellers when operating at maximum efficiency settings. The stagger positions also affect the propeller performance as the propellers see different inflow conditions when placed downstream of adjacent propellers. Moore and Ning [3] numerically examined several design parameters in DEP configurations, including the number of propellers, propeller diameters, and tip speeds, with DEP performance metrics such as total thrust, wing lift coefficient, and take-off roll distance. When compared to the baseline two-propeller configuration, the optimised eight-propeller DEP configuration with optimal diameters can reduce the take-off roll distance by over 80% with more than twice the wing lift coefficient obtained only at the price of 11% of total aircraft mass according to their report. Wingtip-mounted propellers have also been of interest in recent studies and are widely considered in DEP configurations [4-7]. Sinnige et al. [4] experimentally analysed the aerodynamic characteristics of a wingtip-mounted propeller and compared it to a conventional propeller configuration. A reduction in wing drag of 15% at the lift coefficient of 0.5 with a propeller thrust coefficient of 0.12 is observed when the wingtip propeller is rotating in the opposite direction of the wingtip vortex. This results from the propeller slipstream attenuating the wingtip vortex, thus reducing the induced drag.

The noise emitted by the multi-propeller DEP system is also researched due to the urban operating environment of the UAM aircraft [8-17]. Turhan et al. [13] reported that the farfield noise is significantly affected by the propeller advance ratio on a leading edge-mounted two-propeller DEP configuration, with increasing the advance ratio, decreasing the far-field noise level at a fixed rotational speed of 8000 RPM. They also found that the propeller tip clearance of 1% propeller diameter produces slightly larger Sound Pressure Level (SPL) at Blade Passing Frequency (BPF) than a tip clearance of 4% propeller diameter. de Paola [14] et al. examined the relationship between the tonal noise at the first BPF and the angle of attack of a three-propeller DEP configuration,

with an observation of an apparent reduction of noise levels at higher AoAs. Moreover, propeller blade phase angle control has also been shown to be an effective method of reducing the noise emitted to the farfield both numerically and experimentally [2, 15-17], with no significant effects on propeller thrusts.

This paper examines experimentally and numerically the aerodynamic and aeroacoustic characteristics of four different leading edge-mounted DEP configurations, and aims to investigate and compare the aerodynamic and aeroacoustic characteristics of four common DEP configurations, as well as establish a fundamental parametric study for the effect of combined-size propeller DEP configurations and different propeller positions along the wing at different angles of attack. The wind tunnel experiments are conducted at the University of Bristol Wind Tunnel Facilities, and the aerodynamic characteristics of both the propeller and wing of four configurations are compared. Numerical simulations based on the Vortex Particle Method (VPM) are also conducted for all configurations under selected operating conditions to compare the aerodynamics and aeroacoustics characteristics of different DEP configurations. This paper is structured as follows: the first part of Section III illustrates the experimental setup for all four DEP configurations and test campaigns examined in this study; the numerical methodology and setup for mid-fidelity simulations are also presented later in the section. Section IV summarises the aerodynamic performance of the four DEP configurations for both propellers and the wing. These results are compared to identify the difference between these DEP arrangements. Next, numerical VPM results of all configurations under a selected operating case are illustrated in Section V to compare with experimental results, and provide aeroacoustic analysis and comparison for different DEP configurations. Finally, conclusions and future works for the full paper are summarised in Section VI.

III. Methodology

A. Experimental Setup.

The DEP configurations are being tested in the Low-Speed Wind Tunnel at the University of Bristol. This facility is a closed-loop wind tunnel, and has an octagonal test section measuring 2.1m by 1.5m, with a maximum testing wind speed of 60m/s. Equipped with an ATE AEROTECH AID-010-12394-A six-component overhead balance which measures lift, drag, side force, pitch moment, yaw moment, and roll moment, the aerodynamic characteristic of the wing can be accurately captured. Additionally, the overhead balance serves as a turntable, allowing the wing to be tested at various angles of attack throughout the experiment.

Figure 1 illustrates the schematics of all four DEP configurations. The 12-12-12 configuration is selected as the baseline case for comparison. The second configuration replaces the outboard 12-inch propeller with a 15-inch propeller, which is positioned near the wingtip and will be referred to as the 12-12-15 configuration in the following text. The third configuration replaces the inboard 12-inch propeller with a 15-inch propeller, with 12-inch propellers installed at the mid and outboard positions. This configuration is indicated as the 15-12-12 configuration. For both 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 configurations, the 15-inch propellers operate at a lower rotational speed than the 12-inch propellers to maintain the same thrust as the two 12-inch propellers. Finally, the fourth configuration involves only two propellers with the same tip clearance as the baseline configuration and is referred to as the 12-12 configuration in this context. As in previous cases, the total thrust of the 12-12 configuration is matched the same as the baseline configuration, which leads to higher propeller rotational speeds of each of the two propellers.

The rectangular wing uses a NACA 0018 airfoil profile with a chord length of 0.464m and a semispan of 1.375m, primarily manufactured through 3D printing with several materials such as Nylon 12, PLA, and Clear Resin. The baseline (Fig. 1 (a) LHS) and the 12-12 configurations (Fig. 1 (a) RHS) utilise three/two identical propellers of 12-inch (0.305m) diameter made from fibre/epoxy-based materials. The 15-12-12 (Fig. 1 (b) LHS) and 12-12-15 configurations (Fig. 1 (b) RHS) replace one 12-inch propeller with an aluminium-made propeller of 15 inches (0.381m) in diameter. Both 12 and 15-inch propellers have five blades with Clark-Y aerofoil profile, the same pitch-to-diameter ratio of $P/D = 1$ and a hub diameter of 0.075m. All the propellers in all four configurations are in the co-rotating direction, spinning CCW when viewed from the front. Figure 2 illustrates the DEP configurations in the testing section of the wind tunnel. The wing is directly mounted onto the overhead balance outside the testing section, and the wind tunnel ceiling acts as the side plate for the wing with a circular patch at the end of the wing that allows the angle of attack to be altered. The distances from the wind tunnel ceiling to the inboard propeller of the baseline and 12-12 configurations are 0.435m and 0.594m respectively. Both configurations have the same propeller-to-propeller spacing of $s/D_{12inch} = 1.04$, where s is the hub-to-hub distance. For the 15-12-12 and 12-12-15 configurations, the distance from the inboard propeller hub to the wind tunnel ceiling is 0.435m. The tip clearance between the two 12-inch propellers in both cases is 4% of D_{12inch} , and 17% of D_{12inch} between the 12- and 15-inch propellers.

(a) Schematics of baseline (12-12-12) and 12-12 configurations.

(b) Schematics of 15-12-12 and 12-12-15 configurations.

(c) Schematics of the side view of baseline configuration

Fig. 1 Schematics of: (a) Front view of baseline configuration (LHS) and 12-12 configuration (RHS), (b) Front view of 15-12-12 configuration (LHS) and 12-12-15 configuration (RHS) and (c) side view of baseline configuration. All propellers are spinning CCW when viewed at the front. Dimensions shown in mm.

Fig. 2 Images of the baseline (top left), 12-12 (top right), 15-12-12 (bottom left) and 12-12-15 (bottom right) DEP configurations in wind tunnel test section.

To drive each propeller, the propulsion unit consists of a brushless motor, an electric speed controller (ESC), a laser tachometer, and a load cell. The current setup utilises T-MOTOR AT7215 30CC KV270 brushless motors and T-MOTOR AT115A6-14S ESC units. In order to control RPM precisely, a closed-loop PID controller is established in the National Instruments LabVIEW, which receives RPM reading inputs from Monarch 6180-029 ROLS-P laser tachometers. The tachometers are installed outside the wind tunnel test section. Thrust

measurements for the propellers are obtained through three load cells: two six-axis ATI Mini 40 F/T sensors positioned behind the inboard and outboard propellers, and a Futek MBA 500 biaxial load cell with two Futek IAA 100 channel amplifiers for the middle propeller. The ATI Mini 40 load cells support a maximum thrust (z-axis) force range of 240 N and a maximum torque of 4Nm, while the Futek MBA 500 paired with the IAA 100 amplifiers has a certified range of up to 100 lbf (444.8 N) and 10 Nm in both CW and CCW directions. Prior to testing, all load cells are calibrated using a set of known weights and correctly zeroed before each test run. For consistency, a sanity check is conducted by placing all three load cells individually in the same position within the wind tunnel under identical conditions. The Futek load cell and one ATI Mini 40 load cell are referenced to the second ATI Mini 40 load cell to account for any differences due to different load cell models and ranges. Uncertainty and errorbar analysis are also performed to accurately determine the aerodynamic performance of the propellers and wing. The error bar calculations involved the uncertainties of all aspects from the force, propeller rotational speed and wind speed measurements. These include the load cell and overhead balance measurements, the tachometer measurements and the wind speed pitot tube measurements. Propeller thrust and torque data are acquired using the National Instruments PXIe-01926Q chassis with three separate PXIe-6341 modules and processed in MATLAB at the same sampling frequency for a duration of 16 seconds.

B. Experimental test matrix.

A series of testing conditions for each of the four DEP configurations is listed in Table 1. The inflow speed tested in the current study is 10m/s. The AoA varies from -1° to 14° for all configurations to evaluate and compare the lift and drag curves. The propeller rotational speeds of the baseline 12-12-12 configurations are 3000, 4000 and 5000 RPMs at each AoA with an accuracy of ± 3 RPM. For the 15-12-12 and 12-12-15 configurations, the two 12-inch propellers remain at 3000, 4000 and 5000 RPM, while the rotational speeds of the 15-inch propeller are reduced to obtain the same thrust. In the 12-12 case, the propeller rotational speeds for both propellers arise as more thrust is needed from each propeller.

Table 1 Experiment testing cases for all four DEP configurations.

Configuration	RPMs	Inflow speed U_∞ (m/s)	Angle of attack ($^\circ$)
Baseline (12-12-12)	3000, 4000, 5000	10	-1, 0, 2, 5, 8, 10, 12, 14
15-12-12 12-12-15	3000 (2050), 4000 (2650), 5000 (3250)	10	-1, 0, 2, 5, 8, 10, 12, 14
12-12	3000 (3400), 4000 (4700)	10	-1, 0, 2, 5, 8, 10, 12, 14

C. Computational setup.

The coupled aerodynamic and aeroacoustic characteristics between the propellers and wing are simulated using a mid-fidelity computational tool, as outlined in the configurations shown in Fig 1. In these setups, a set of virtual microphones is defined to enable noise analysis and comparison across different configurations. This computational tool applies unsteady potential flow methods, utilising the Vortex Lattice Method (VLM) to simulate aerodynamic surfaces. The VLM represents thin surfaces with a grid of quadrilateral vortex ring elements made of constant-strength vortex filaments. By applying the Biot-Savart law with a finite vortex core size, the velocity induced by each vortex filament, with strength γ and endpoints at positions \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 , can be calculated at an evaluation point \mathbf{r}_0 :

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \frac{\gamma}{4\pi} \frac{(\|\mathbf{r}_1\| + \|\mathbf{r}_2\|)(\|\mathbf{r}_1\|\|\mathbf{r}_2\| - \mathbf{r}_1 \cdot \mathbf{r}_2)}{\|\mathbf{r}_1\|\|\mathbf{r}_2\|(\|\mathbf{r}_1 \times \mathbf{r}_2\|^2 + r_c^2\|\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1\|^2)}, \quad (1)$$

where $r_c = \sqrt{\alpha_L \nu \delta t}$, α_L is Lamb's constant, ν is the kinematic viscosity and $\delta = 1 + a_1 \frac{\gamma}{\nu}$, where a_1 is the Squire's parameter and γ the vortex filament strength. Each vortex element includes a collocation point, enforcing a Neumann boundary condition to ensure zero normal flow velocity at the surface. This condition allows for the assembly and solution of a linear system of equations, which defines the strength of each panel based on the flow velocity at each collocation point.

In contrast to conventional unsteady VLM and panel approaches, the wake behind an aerodynamic surface here is not modelled by a deformable sheet of vortex rings. Instead, vortex particles based on the Vortex Particle Method (VPM) represent the wake, describing it as discrete fluid packets (particles). This particle-based wake approach avoids issues related to mesh distortion and entanglement, especially during interactions among wakes and between wakes and surfaces in multi-surface scenarios. The VPM arises from a discrete form of the Vorticity

Transport Equation, which is itself derived from the incompressible Navier-Stokes momentum equation. By assuming the velocity field induced by vortex particles is divergence-free (solenoidal), Green's function enables a solution for this field. This velocity field can then be combined with the irrotational field induced by VLM surface elements via Helmholtz's decomposition. The specifics of the VPM implementation used in this simulation are presented below, with further details and derivations available in [18-20]. The evolution of the particle circulation is given by Eq. 2 to 4:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \Gamma_p(t) = (\Gamma_p(t) \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_p(t), t) + \frac{d}{dt} \Gamma_p^{visc}, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{x}_p(t) = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}_p(t), t) = \sum_q K(\mathbf{x}_p(t), \mathbf{x}_q(t)) \times \Gamma_p(t), \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \Gamma_p^{visc} = \frac{105}{4\pi\sigma^5} \sum_q \frac{V_p \Gamma_q - V_q \Gamma_p}{\left[\left(\frac{\|\mathbf{x}_p - \mathbf{x}_q\|}{\sigma} \right)^2 + 1 \right]^{\frac{9}{2}}}, \quad (4)$$

where σ represents the particle smoothing length, and the particle kernel $K(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$, follows the formulation of Winkelmanns and Leonard [19], and the viscous component in VPM is evaluated using a Particle Strength Exchange scheme. A new row of particles is initialised at the trailing edge of each aerodynamic surface at each time step, with their strengths derived from the vortex ring strengths at the trailing edge of the previous time step. Once the aerodynamic solution is complete, Farassat's Formulation 1A [21] of the Ffowcs-Williams and Hawkings equation is applied to compute acoustic propagation from surfaces within the fluid domain. Monopole and dipole source effects are included, derived from the pressure distribution on aerodynamic surfaces, while quadrupole sources from the volume are omitted. These computational methods are implemented in a framework which enables large-scale vectorisation and parallel processing, significantly accelerating time-to-solution.

(a) Baseline configuration

(b) 12-12 configuration

Fig. 3 (a) and (b) Panel models for: (a) baseline configuration and (b) 12-12 configuration.

In this study, the wing is modelled with 80 span-wise panels uniformly distributed and 16 chord-wise panels in a cosine distribution across the upper and lower surfaces, resulting in 2560 panels. Each propeller is modelled with five blades, each comprising 41 span-wise panels and 24 chord-wise panels, totalling 984 panels per blade or 4920 panels per propeller. The VLM model, therefore, contains 17320 for the baseline configuration and 12400 panels for the 12-12 configuration. Figure 3 show two examples of the panel model for the baseline and 12-12 configurations. Simulations are conducted over a total of 15 propeller revolutions, with each time step representing a 2-degree propeller rotation. It should be noted that in all VPM simulations, no wind tunnel ceiling or floor is simulated; only the propellers and the wing are investigated. As each configuration has its own rotational speeds, Table 2 summarises the simulation parameters for each case, containing the total physical simulation time, the timestep length, the number of timesteps and the frequency resolution obtained.

Table 2 Simulation parameters.

Configuration	RPM	Total Revolutions	Angular Displacement per Time Step	Simulation Time (s)	Time Step (s)	Number of Time Steps	Frequency Resolution (Hz)
baseline	4000	15	2	0.225	8.334E-05	2700	4.44
12-12-15	4000/2700	~15/10	2/1.35	0.22	8.333E-05	2667	4.55
15-12-12	2700/4000	10/~15	1.35/2	0.22	8.333E-05	2667	4.55
12-12	4700	10	2	0.13	7.092E-05	1800	7.69

Figure 4 shows the schematics of the noise planes utilised for the noise analysis in this work. The propeller plane is defined as the spanwise plane which contains all the propellers, with $\phi = 0^\circ$ at the outboard wing and $\phi = 90^\circ$ directly above the wing. The longitudinal plane is set chordwise at the midpoint of the wingspan, with the $\theta = 0^\circ$ directly in front of the wing. Therefore, for all configurations in this study, the longitudinal plane remains the same. The two planes intersect with each other at $\phi = \theta = 90^\circ$. To account for tonal noise generated by both the 12-inch and 15-inch propellers, the SPL is integrated over one-third-octave bands centred on the first Blade-Passing Frequency (BPF) of the 12-inch propeller operating at 4000 RPM for the 12-12-12 configuration, and 4700 RPM for the 12-12 configuration. Thus, the integrated frequency range of the 1st BPF is given by:

$$f \in \left[\frac{BPF}{octave\ factor}, BPF \times octave\ factor \right], \quad (5a)$$

For the 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 configurations, the frequency band is performed through:

$$f \in \left[\frac{BPF_{15inch}}{octave\ factor}, BPF_{12inch} \times octave\ factor \right], \quad (5b)$$

$$BPF = \frac{B \times RPM}{60}, \quad (5c)$$

and the octave factor is $2^{1/6}$.

Fig. 4 Schematics of the propeller and longitudinal plane for the aeroacoustics analysis in this study.

IV. Experimental Results

This section summarises the aerodynamic results and analysis from the experiments conducted on all four configurations studied in this work. The propeller aerodynamic results are first presented in this section for the baseline, 12-12-15, 15-12-12, and 12-12 configurations. For each configuration, thrust and torque for all propellers are plotted against the angle of attack of the wing, followed by the thrust, torque and power coefficients C_T , C_Q and C_P plots against AoA at different RPMs. These non-dimensional coefficients are analysed to enable performance comparison across configurations and different operating RPMs, independent of propeller sizes. In particular, examining C_T and C_P as functions of wing angles of attack and thrust provides more insight into the aerodynamic loading and power demand characteristics of each setup. Finally, the C_T , C_P and propeller efficiency η are plotted against the propeller thrust. This analysis is crucial for identifying optimal operating conditions, understanding and comparing thrust generation and power consumption of different propeller sizes and positions, and eventually providing guidelines for the efficient design of future DEP systems. The second part of this section compares and discusses the overall wing performance of the clean wing and all four configurations. The clean wing performance is tested in the wind tunnel without any propulsion units mounted at the leading edge of the wing.

A. Propeller aerodynamic performance results.

A.1. Propeller performance of the baseline (12-12-12) configuration.

Figure 5 illustrates the thrust and torque against AoAs at 3000, 4000 and 5000 RPMs. It can be noticed that the outboard propeller thrust slightly fluctuates with the angles of attack in all cases, whereas the thrust from both inboard and mid propellers is relatively constant. At higher propeller rotational speeds and angles of attack, the mid propeller thrust drops compared to the inboard propeller, especially when the rotational speed increases to 5000 RPM, where the mid propeller thrust reduces by around 7% at $\text{AoA} = 14^\circ$. The torque of three propellers remains similar at 3000 and 4000 RPMs, whereas the torque of the mid propeller marginally outruns the inboard and outboard propellers only at high AoAs at 5000 RPM. This larger difference at the mid propeller position at 5000 RPM might be because of the propeller slipstream speed increment of the adjacent propellers, and also the

Fig. 5 (a-f) Thrust and torque against AoA at: (a) and (b), 3000 RPM, (c) and (d), 4000 RPM, (e) and (f), 5000 RPM of the baseline (12-12-12) configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$.

larger axial velocities induced by the adjacent propellers upstream of the mid propeller. de Vries et al. [2] mentioned that the majority of the thrust loss is caused by the installation of the nacelles, resulting in an increment of flow speed locally at the mid propeller position.

The propeller thrust, torque and power coefficients are plotted in Fig. 6 at different RPMs. These coefficients C_T , C_Q and C_P are given by Eq. 6:

$$C_T = \frac{T}{\rho n^2 D^4}, \quad (6a)$$

$$C_Q = \frac{Q}{\rho n^2 D^5}, \quad (6b)$$

$$C_P = \frac{P}{\rho n^3 D^5}, \quad (6c)$$

where D , T and Q are the propeller diameter, measured thrust and torque, respectively. n is the propeller rotational speed in revolutions per second, and ρ is the air density. The propeller power P can then be calculated as $P = 2\pi nQ$. These non-dimensionalised coefficients will help identify the difference between the three propeller positions throughout the AoA sweep, as well as later for the comparison of propeller sizes across different rotational speeds. In general, C_T of the outboard propeller fluctuates as the AoA changes at different rotational speeds, especially at 3000 RPM. Meanwhile, the C_Q of the mid propeller is also marginally lower than that of the inboard propeller at 3000 RPM, whereas the C_P for the three propeller positions is roughly similar. For 4000 and 5000 RPMs, the thrust coefficient of the mid propeller is slightly lower than the inboard for most AoAs. The difference in the torque and power coefficients for all three propellers is not significant throughout the AoA sweep, except that at higher AoAs of 5000 RPM, the mid propeller has a higher C_Q and C_P compared to the other positions.

Fig. 6 (a-i) C_T , C_Q and C_P against AoA at: (a-c), 3000 RPM, (d-f), 4000 RPM and (g-i), 5000 RPM of the baseline (12-12-12) configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$.

The C_T , C_P and propeller efficiency η of each propeller of the 12-12-12 configuration against the propeller thrust are illustrated in Fig. 7 at AoA = 0° and 5°. The propeller efficiency is given by:

$$\eta = \frac{C_T J}{C_Q} \quad (7a)$$

$$J = \frac{U_\infty}{nD} \quad (7b)$$

where U_∞ is the inflow velocity seen by the propeller. We notice that for the two angles of attack studied in this work, the general trends of these plots remain the same. For the C_T plots, the thrust coefficients are similar at lower thrusts, while the difference increases as thrust grows, with the outboard being the highest, the mid propeller the lowest among the three. As mentioned earlier, when operating at the same propeller rotational speed, the thrust of the mid propeller is the lowest compared to the other two as thrust increases. The C_P difference across the three propeller positions is not significant with the uncertainty analysis mentioned in Section III. The efficiency of the outboard propeller is marginally higher than that of the inboard propeller at 0° AoA. For both angles of attack, the efficiency of the mid propeller initially exceeds that of the inboard and outboard propellers at low thrust, but then drops dramatically as thrust increases. This corresponds to the discussions made earlier in the session, as propeller thrust increases, the C_T of the mid propeller drops below the other two propellers, and eventually results in a reduction in propeller efficiency at high thrusts.

Fig. 7 (a-f) C_T , C_P and η against propeller thrust at: (a-c), AoA = 0°, (d-f), AoA = 5° of the baseline (12-12-12) configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$, thrust increases as propeller rotational speed increases.

A.2. Propeller performance of the 12-12-15 configuration.

The 12-12-15 configuration replaces the outboard 12-inch propeller of the baseline configuration with a 15-inch propeller, while maintaining the same mid and inboard propeller positions. This makes the outboard 15-inch propeller closer to the wingtip, where the flowfield is expected to be more complex. Figure 8 displays the thrust and torque variations with the angle of attack of the wing. To match the thrust with the baseline configuration, the rotational speeds of the 15-inch propeller are decreased to 2050, 2650, and 3250 RPMs, corresponding to 3000, 4000, and 5000 RPMs for the 12-inch propellers. For all the following discussions, the rotational speeds of the 15-inch propellers are always referred to the 12-inch propellers; readers should be reminded that the 15-inch propellers are actually spinning at a lower RPM as specified above. It can be noticed that similar to the baseline configuration, at higher rotational speeds, the mid propeller thrust decreases when compared to the inboard 12-inch propeller, especially at higher angles of attack. The largest thrust difference occurs at 5000 RPM. The difference in torque required for the two 12-inch propellers is negligible at all propeller rotational speeds and AoAs. Nonetheless, the torque required for the outboard 15-inch propeller is significantly greater than that of the 12-inch propellers, given that the thrust produced by both propellers is roughly the same.

Fig. 8 (a-f) Thrust and torque against AoA at: (a) and (b), 3000 RPM, (c) and (d), 4000 RPM, (e) and (f), 5000 RPM of the 12-12-15 configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$.

The thrust, torque and power coefficient plots are provided in Fig. 9. Similar to the baseline configuration, the thrust and torque coefficients increase as the propeller rotational speeds rises. At higher AoAs of 3000 and 4000 RPM, the 12-inch mid propeller C_T is lower than the inboard 12-inch propeller. However, at 5000 RPM, the C_T for the mid propeller is consistently lower than that of the inboard propeller. C_Q and C_P for both 12-inch propellers are the same, and they increase slightly as propeller rotational speed grows. All coefficients for the 15-inch propeller increase dramatically as rotational speed increases when compared to the increment of the 12-inch propellers from 3000 to 5000 RPM. C_T , C_Q and C_P for the outboard 15-inch are significantly lower than those for the two 12-inch propellers at 3000 RPM, whereas at 4000 RPM, this difference diminishes. At 5000 RPM, the C_P of the 15-inch propeller is only marginally higher than the 12-inch propellers at AoAs below 10° . The fluctuation of the outboard propeller still exists, which suggests an unsteady loading seen by the blade at outboard positions.

Fig. 9 (a-i) C_T , C_Q and C_P against AoA at: (a-c), 3000 RPM, (d-f), 4000 RPM and (g-i), 5000 RPM of the 12-15 configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$.

Fig. 10 (a-f) C_T , C_P and η against propeller thrust at: (a-c), AoA = 0°, (d-f), AoA = 5° of the 12-12-15 configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$, thrust increases as propeller rotational speed increases.

Figure 10 depicts the thrust and power coefficients, and the propeller efficiency against the produced thrust. As seen in the baseline configuration, the change of AoA does not alter the general trend of the C_T , C_P and efficiency relationships between the propellers. Here, for all thrusts, the efficiency of the 15-inch propeller is constantly higher than that of the 12-inch propeller. The thrust and power coefficients of the 15-inch propeller are lower than those of the 12-inch propellers at low thrusts. As the thrust increases, the differences between them reduce, and eventually, C_P exceeds that of the 12-inch propeller, whereas C_T remains roughly the same as the 12-inch propellers.

A.3. Propeller performance of the 15-12-12 configuration.

The 15-12-12 configuration replaces the inboard 12-inch propeller with a 15-inch propeller and shifts the mid propeller downwards to the wingtip compared to the 12-12-15 configuration. The inboard and outboard propeller

Fig. 11 (a-f) Thrust and torque against AoA at: (a) and (b), 3000 RPM, (c) and (d), 4000 RPM, (e) and (f), 5000 RPM of the 15-12-12 configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$.

positions for both 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 are identical, apart from that one has the 15-inch propeller outboard closer to the wingtip and the other closer to the wind tunnel ceiling or the side plate. Figure 11 shows the thrust and torque plots against the angles of attack at different propeller rotational speeds. In order to maintain the same thrust, the rotational speeds of the inboard propellers are reduced to 2050, 2650 and 3250 RPMs, respectively. Furthermore, from the thrust plots, it can be observed that as the AoA increases, the inboard 15-inch propeller thrust also increases. Therefore, during the experiment, the rotational speeds for the 15-inch propeller were intentionally tuned down step-by-step by 150 RPM as the angle of attack changed from -1° to 14° to ensure that the total thrust remained within the same range as the baseline configurations. In this configuration, the mid propeller also produces lower thrust than the outboard 12-inch propeller in all cases. In addition, when compared to the baseline configuration, the thrust of the mid propeller is consistently lower than that of the other 12-inch propeller for most positive angles of attack. Han et al. [22] looked into a different DEP configuration experimentally, where three identical 15-inch propellers are mounted at the leading edge. It was concluded that at the same operating conditions, the triple 15-inch propeller configurations exhibit less mid-propeller thrust reduction than the 12-12-12 configuration when producing the same thrust. Therefore, the mid propeller thrust reductions seen on both combined-size DEP configurations indicate that, apart from the propeller nacelle blockage, the propeller upstream contraction and slipstream interactions also play essential roles in affecting the blade loading of the propeller. The torque required for the 12-inch propellers is roughly the same throughout the AoA sweep, and the torque required for the 15-inch propeller is considerably higher than both 12-inch propellers. The measured torque for both 12-inch propellers is the same, as similar to the 12-12-15 configuration.

Fig. 12 (a-i) C_T , C_Q and C_P against AoA at: (a-c), 3000 RPM, (d-f), 4000 RPM and (g-i), 5000 RPM of the 15-12-12 configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$.

Figure 12 demonstrates the corresponding thrust and torque coefficient plots for the 15-12-12 configuration. Similar to the baseline configuration, both C_T and C_Q increase as propeller rotational speed rises from 3000 to 5000 RPM, and the C_P of both 12-inch propellers remains roughly the same from 4000 to 5000 RPM. The thrust

coefficient fluctuation of the outboard propeller remains identifiable, and its C_T outperforms both the mid and inboard propellers at most AoAs, whereas the torque coefficients are roughly the same as those of the mid 12-inch propeller. On the other hand, the inboard 15-inch propeller has the lowest C_T and C_Q at 3000 RPM. When the RPM increases to 4000 and 5000, the difference between the 15- and 12-inch propellers in terms of thrust coefficients decreases, while this difference almost disappears for the torque coefficients at 4000 RPM. This phenomenon is also found in the previous discussion of the 12-12-15 configuration, where the 15-inch propeller is installed at the outboard position. At the lower AoAs in the 5000 RPM case, the 15-inch propeller has a marginally higher C_P than the other propellers.

Fig. 13 (a-f) C_T , C_P and η against propeller thrust at: (a-c), $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$, (d-f), $\text{AoA} = 5^\circ$ of the 15-12-12 configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$, thrust increases as propeller rotational speed increases.

Similar to the previous configurations, the change of AoA does not alter the general trend of the C_T , C_P and efficiency relationships between the propellers, as shown in Fig. 13. The C_T of the inboard 15-inch propeller is lower than that of the 12-inch propellers at lower thrusts, and it increases significantly as the propeller thrust increases. The C_P of both 12-inch propellers is similar, whereas the 15-inch propeller has the lowest C_P at low thrusts and the highest C_P at higher thrusts. The efficiency of the 15-inch propeller at higher thrusts is higher than the 12-inch propellers, and the efficiency of the 12-inch mid propeller is lower than the other 12-inch outboard propeller under most thrust settings. This is more pronounced at 5° AoA. When compared to the 12-12-15 configuration, it can be seen that the general trend for the thrust and torque coefficients against propeller thrust of the 12- and 15-inch propellers is similar, except for the propeller efficiency plots. The efficiency difference between the 12- and 15-inch propellers is not as significant as seen in the 12-12-15 configuration at lower thrusts; this difference only becoming identifiable at higher thrusts at both angles of attack, with the 15-inch propellers have higher efficiencies than the 12-inch propellers

A.4. Propeller performance of the 12-12 configuration.

The equivalent rotational speeds for the 12-inch propeller on the dual propeller DEP configuration are 3400 and 4700 RPMs, so that they will produce the same amount of thrust as the baseline triple propeller configuration. Figure 14 and 15 depict the thrust and torque and their corresponding C_T , C_Q and C_P changes with angles of attack as analysed in previous sections. The thrust plots indicate that the thrust fluctuations observed at previous outboard positions decrease noticeably, and the difference in thrust and torque between the two propellers is negligible. A slight increment is observed in the C_T plots at 3000 RPM, while only minimal differences in torque coefficient are observed for both propeller rotational speeds. The difference between the C_P is also negligible.

Fig. 14 (a-d) Thrust and torque against AoA at: (a) and (b), 3000 RPM, (c) and (d), 4000 RPM of 12-12 configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$.

Fig. 15 (a-f) C_T , C_Q and C_P against AoA at: (a-c), 3000 RPM, (d-f), 4000 RPM of 12-12 configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$.

Figure 16 illustrates the C_T , C_P and efficiency η plots against the propeller thrust. Due to the difference in C_Q at 3000 RPM as mentioned above, the efficiency of the inboard propeller is slightly higher than that of the outboard propeller at lower thrust. The AoA does not change the behaviour of the propeller performance, as found in all other configurations.

Fig. 16 (a-f) C_T , C_P and η against propeller thrust at: (a-c), $\text{AoA} = 0^\circ$, (d-f), $\text{AoA} = 5^\circ$ of 12-12 configuration at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$, thrust increases as propeller RPM increases.

B. Wing performance comparison.

Figure 17 outlines the lift and drag coefficients and the C_L/C_D ratio against AoA of the clean wing along with all four different configurations. Of all configurations studied in this work, the 12-12 configuration has comparatively lower lift coefficients and higher drag coefficients among all the configurations across most AoAs. Consequently, the C_L/C_D ratio for the dual propeller configuration is the lowest, with the maximum C_L/C_D ratio of the 12-12 configuration being approximately 35% lower than that of the baseline configuration at 4000 RPM. The worst performance of the dual propeller configuration in terms of lift-to-drag ratio might be caused by the lack of one propeller, and hence a high-lift region exerted on the wing, as a result of the high-speed slip stream behind the propeller. In addition, the drag of the 12-12 configuration is the highest, suggesting a possible reduction of induced drag on the three-propeller configurations. Among the three-propeller configurations, when operating at lower propeller rotational speeds, the wing performance of the baseline configuration outperforms both the 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 configurations at most AoAs, with an approximately 16% higher maximum C_L/C_D ratio than the other two. However, in the 4000 RPM case, 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 perform slightly better than the baseline configuration at lower AoAs. This may imply a better take-off performance as generally higher RPMs are required at take-offs. The difference between the wing aerodynamic performance of the 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 configurations is minimal across most of the AoAs, with the 12-12-15 configuration having slightly improved performance than the 15-12-12 configuration at lower AoAs. Looking into the literature, studies [5-7] have reported that the wing tip-mounted propeller can reduce the induced drag of the wing and improve the lift coefficient, hence wing the performance. However, as illustrated in the schematics in Fig. 1, in this work the 15-inch propeller is not exactly tip-mounted; therefore, the aerodynamic interactions between the outboard propeller and wingtip vortex still need to be studied. The following section presents the numerical simulation results, which will help validate the experimental results and provide insights into the aeroacoustics characteristics of the investigated DEP configurations.

V. Numerical Results

This section presents numerical results from the VPM simulations as described in Section III. The case selected for this study is the baseline configuration at 4000 RPM, along with equivalent propeller rotational speeds for other configurations as stated in the previous section. All configurations are operating at $\text{AoA} = 5^\circ$ and

Fig. 17 (a-d) Experimental wing aerodynamic performance at $U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$ of: (a), C_L against AoA at 3000 RPM, (b), C_D against AoA at 3000 RPM, (c), C_L/C_D ratio against AoA at 3000 RPM, and (d), C_L/C_D ratio against AoA at 4000 RPM.

$U_\infty = 10\text{m/s}$. Thrust and torque coefficient comparisons between numerical and experimental results are first shown. This is followed by DEP noise directivity and spectrum plots to illustrate the aeroacoustic differences between these configurations.

A. Thrust and torque coefficient comparisons.

Table 3 and 4 summarise the propeller thrust and torque coefficients from the experiment and numerical VPM simulations as described in Section III. In general, the thrust coefficient predictions for the 12-inch propellers show good agreement with the experiments with around 5% difference. However, for the outboard 12-inch propeller for the 15-12-12 configuration, the difference reaches 10%. In contrast, VPM underpredicts the thrust of the 15-inch propellers by about 10% compared to the experimental results. In terms of the torque prediction, for all three-propeller configurations, the mid propeller has the best agreement. The percentage differences between the inboard and outboard propellers are relatively significant, ranging from 10% to 17%. The numerical simulations seem to underpredict the inboard propeller torque, whereas they exaggerate it at the outboard position. The highest discrepancy between the numerical and experimental results is observed in the torque prediction of the 12-12 configuration, where the inboard propeller torque is underpredicted by 26% and the outboard propeller by approximately 18%.

Table 3 Thrust coefficient comparisons between numerical and experimental results for all propellers on the 12-12-12, 15-12-12, 12-12-15, and 12-12 configurations at 4000 equivalent RPM, AoA = 5° and $U_\infty = 10$ m/s.

Thrust coefficients C_T	Inboard propeller			Mid propeller			Outboard propeller		
	Experimental	Numerical	Percentage difference	Experimental	Numerical	Percentage difference	Experimental	Numerical	Percentage difference
12-12-12 configuration	0.184	0.173	5.92%	0.180	0.174	3.41%	0.185	0.174	6.04%
15-12-12 configuration	0.167	0.150	10.47%	0.180	0.174	3.34%	0.192	0.173	9.88%
12-12-15 configuration	0.182	0.173	4.53%	0.180	0.174	3.06%	0.167	0.150	10.18%
12-12 configuration	0.199	0.188	5.43%	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.197	0.189	4.17%

Table 4 Torque coefficient comparisons between numerical and experimental results for all propellers on the 12-12-12, 15-12-12, 12-12-15, and 12-12 configurations at 4000 equivalent RPM, AoA = 5° and $U_\infty = 10$ m/s.

Torque coefficients C_Q	Inboard propeller			Mid propeller			Outboard propeller		
	Experimental	Numerical	Percentage difference	Experimental	Numerical	Percentage difference	Experimental	Numerical	Percentage difference
12-12-12 configuration	0.024	0.022	8.89%	0.024	0.025	-4.22%	0.024	0.028	-14.78%
15-12-12 configuration	0.024	0.021	14.65%	0.025	0.026	-5.44%	0.025	0.029	-16.87%
12-12-15 configuration	0.025	0.022	10.06%	0.024	0.025	-1.83%	0.023	0.026	-11.26%
12-12 configuration	0.025	0.019	25.52%	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.025	0.020	17.72%

B. Noise directivities and spectrum comparisons.

Figure 18 illustrates the 1st BPF noise directivity plots of DEP noise for all four configurations from the VPM simulations. To account for tonal noise generated by both the 12-inch and 15-inch propellers, the SPL is integrated over the frequency band stated in Section III. The longitudinal and propeller planes are also defined in Section III. This ensures a consistent bandwidth analysis, regardless of different rotational speeds and BPFs. The directivity plots here illustrate the overall DEP system noise emitted, which contains all aspects, including all propeller noise, wing noise and other interaction noises, and they are plotted in both propeller and longitudinal planes as shown in Fig.17. In general, the dipolar-shaped noise directivity patterns seen in both planes are similar for all configurations, with the dual propeller 12-12 configuration exhibiting the highest SPL among all configurations, especially between observer angles of $\varphi = \theta = 45^\circ$ and 315° . The difference between the three-propeller configurations is comparatively small, with the 12-12-15 configuration having a slightly higher SPL at from $\varphi = 90^\circ$ to $\varphi = 270^\circ$ at the propeller plane, whereas the difference is not dramatic at the longitudinal plane.

Fig. 18 (a) and (b) Numerical VPM simulation results of overall DEP system noise directivities between the 12-12-12, 15-12-12, 12-12-15 and 12-12 configurations at 1st BPF of (a), propeller plane, and (b), longitudinal plane at 4000 RPM, α (AoA) = 5° and $U_\infty = 10$ m/s.

Fig. 19 (a-g). Numerical VPM simulation results of overall DEP system noise spectrums for propeller and longitudinal planes between baseline, 15-12-12, 12-12-15 and 12-12 configuration at φ and θ of: (a) and (b), 0° , (c) and (d), 30° , (d) and (e), 60° and (f), 90° at 4000 RPM, AoA = 5° and $U_\infty = 10$ m/s.

Figure 19 illustrates the noise spectra of all configurations for both propeller and longitudinal planes at 0° , 30° , 60° and 90° . As aforementioned, the two planes intersect at $\varphi = \theta = 90^\circ$. For the double-propeller 12-12 configuration, the SPL at 1st BPF is always higher than other configurations for both planes at all studied observer angles, as they are spinning at higher RPM and tip Mach numbers than other propellers. Specifically, at φ and $\theta = 60^\circ$, the SPL at the 1st BPF of the 12-12 configuration is approximately 5 dB higher than the three-propeller configurations in both planes. As observed in the directivity plots, there are only slight differences between the three-propeller configurations at all BPFs, mostly within 5 dB. Because of the presence of a 15-inch propeller, there are two tonal peaks observed on the spectrum of the 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 configurations at two different 1st BPFs. The spectrum for the 12-12-15 is only marginally higher than the baseline and the 15-12-12 configuration at φ and $\theta = 60^\circ$ and 90° .

VI. Conclusions

This study experimentally and numerically investigates the aerodynamic and aeroacoustic characteristics of four different DEP configurations: baseline (12-12-12), 12-12-15, 15-12-12 and 12-12 configurations. The 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 configurations replace an outboard and inboard 12-inch propeller with a 15-inch propeller, respectively. Experiments are carried out at the Wind Tunnel Facilities at the University of Bristol, where the propeller and wing aerodynamic performance are examined. The thrust from the 15-inch propellers is matched the same as the 12-inch propellers, resulting in operating at a lower rotational speed. Current experimental results indicated that for all three-propeller configurations studied, the mid propeller produces slightly lower thrust than adjacent propellers, while the torque required is roughly the same as that of the other propellers. When the 15-inch propeller is at the inboard position, its thrust increases as the wing angle of attack increases. The torque required for the 15-inch propellers is considerably higher than that of the 12-inch propellers, while the thrust and torque coefficients at lower propeller rotational speeds are lower than that of the 12-inch propellers. The change of angles of attack does not affect the general trends of the thrust, torque and power coefficients against the propeller thrust. All these coefficients for the 15-inch propeller increase dramatically with propeller rotational speeds when compared to the 12-inch propeller. The 15-inch propeller mounted at the outboard position exhibits more favourable efficiency performance over all thrust settings than it does at the inboard position. The wing performance comparisons show that the 12-12 has the worst aerodynamic performance in wing lift-to-drag ratio at both propeller rotational speeds. In the lower rotational speed case, the baseline configuration has a better performance among all configurations at most angles of attack, whereas at the higher propeller rotational speeds, both 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 configurations slightly outrun the baseline performance at lower angles of attack. The difference between the 12-12-15 and 15-12-12 is trivial at most angles of attack, with the 12-12-15 configuration only slightly better than the other at several low angles of attack.

Numerical simulations are also carried out using the Vortex Particle Method (VPM). The comparison between the numerical and experimental results shows good thrust agreement on the 12-inch propeller with around 5% difference, whereas higher differences of approximately 10% are observed for the 15-inch propellers. The predicted torque, however, has larger discrepancies between the simulation and the experiments. Noise directivity analysis of all configurations is also performed, with the dual propeller 12-12 configuration emitting the loudest noise at 1st BPF, and the difference between the three-propeller configurations is insignificant. Noise spectra analysis also confirms that the dual propeller configuration has higher SPL levels than other configurations over various observer angles. Higher-fidelity simulation works such as the Lattice-Boltzmann Method (LBM), could also be carried out to further investigate the complex flowfield of the propeller-propeller and propeller-wingtip vortex interactions. Furthermore, advanced flowfield visualisation techniques, along with experimental aeroacoustic measurements, can also be implemented on the combined-size propeller DEP systems to help provide and understand the comprehensive picture of the aerodynamic and aeroacoustic characteristics across the different DEP configurations.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledge financial support from the Horizon Europe research and innovation program for the INDIGO (grant agreement number 101096055), SilentProp (grant agreement number 882842) projects and the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (grant No. EP/W033550/1).

References

- [1] Kim, H. D., Perry, A. T., & Ansell, P. J. (2018). A review of distributed electric propulsion concepts for air vehicle technology. In *2018 AIAA/IEEE Electric Aircraft Technologies Symposium (EATS)* (pp. 1-21). IEEE.
- [2] de Vries, R., van Arnhem, N., Sinnige, T., Vos, R., & Veldhuis, L. L. (2021). Aerodynamic interaction between propellers of a distributed-propulsion system in forward flight. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, *118*, 107009.

- [3] Moore, K. R., & Ning, A. (2018). Distributed electric propulsion effects on existing aircraft through multidisciplinary optimization. In *AIAA ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conference*, Kissimmee, Florida, US.
- [4] Sinnige, T., van Arnhem, N., Stokkermans, T. C., Eitelberg, G., & Veldhuis, L. L. (2019). Wingtip-mounted propellers: Aerodynamic analysis of interaction effects and comparison with conventional layout. *Journal of Aircraft*, 56(1), 295-312.
- [5] Della Vecchia, P., Malgieri, D., Nicolosi, F., & De Marco, A. (2018). Numerical analysis of propeller effects on wing aerodynamic: tip mounted and distributed propulsion. *Transportation research procedia*, 29, 106-115.
- [6] Yoo, S., Duensing, J. C., Deere, K. A., Viken, J. K., & Frederick, M. (2023). Computational analysis on the effects of high-lift propellers and wing-tip cruise propellers on X-57. In *AIAA AVIATION 2023 Forum*, (p. 3382), San Diego, California, US .
- [7] Snyder Jr, M. H., & Zumwalt, G. W. (1969). Effects of wingtip-mounted propellers on wing lift and induced drag. *Journal of Aircraft*, 6(5), 392-397.
- [8] Turhan, B. B., Jawahar, H. K., Rezgui, D., & Azarpeyvand, M. (2025). Characterizing the noise patterns of overlapping propellers in forward flight. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 157(4), 2790-2801.
- [9] Bowen, L., Turhan, B., Kamliya Jawahar, H., Rezgui, D., & Azarpeyvand, M. (2023). Aeroacoustic characteristics of distributed electric propulsion configuration with turbulent flows. In *AIAA AVIATION 2023 Forum* (p. 4294), San Diego, California, US.
- [10] Lopes de Moraes Filho, L. F., Turhan, B. B., Trascinelli, L., Rezgui, D., Azarpeyvand, M., Franco, A., Ewert, R., Zang, B., and Zhou, B. Y. (2025). Assessment of aeroacoustic simulations for the installation noise of a propeller-wing configuration in forward flight using multi-fidelity solvers. In *AIAA AVIATION 2025 Forum*, Las Vegas, US.
- [11] Turhan, B., Jawahar, H. K., Bowen, L., Rezgui, D., & Azarpeyvand, M. (2023). Aeroacoustic characteristics of single propeller-wing configuration. In *International Institute of Acoustics and Vibration, The 29th International Congress on Sound and Vibration*, Prague.
- [12] Turhan, B., Jawahar, H. K., Rezgui, D., and Azarpeyvand, M. (2025) Investigating the Aerodynamic and Aeroacoustic Behavior of a Single Propeller-Wing Configuration in Turbulent Flow. *AIAA AVIATION 2025 Forum*, Las Vegas, US.
- [13] Turhan, B., Kamliya Jawahar, H., Bowen, L., Rezgui, D., & Azarpeyvand, M. (2023). Aeroacoustic characteristics of distributed electric propulsion system in forward flight. In *AIAA Aviation 2023 forum* (p. 4490), San Diego, California, US.
- [14] De Paola, E., Camussi, R., Stoica, G. L., Di Marco, A., & Capobianchi, G. (2024). Aerodynamic and aeroacoustic experimental investigation of a three propellers DEP configuration. *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 154, 109508.
- [15] Turhan, B., Jawahar, H. K., Gautam, A., Syed, S., Vakil, G., Rezgui, D., & Azarpeyvand, M. (2024). Acoustic characteristics of phase-synchronized adjacent propellers. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 155(5), 3242-3253.
- [16] Patterson, A., Gahlawat, A., & Hovakimyan, N. (2019). Propeller phase synchronization for small distributed electric vehicles. In *AIAA Scitech 2019 Forum* (p. 1458), San Diego, California, US.
- [17] Pascioni, K. A., Rizzi, S. A., & Schiller, N. (2019). Noise reduction potential of phase control for distributed propulsion vehicles. In *AIAA scitech 2019 forum* (p. 1069), San Diego, California, US.
- [18] Winckelmans, G.S. (1993) 'Topics in vortex methods for the computation of three- and two-dimensional incompressible unsteady flows', PhD thesis, California Institute of Technology Pasadena, California.
- [19] Winckelmans, G. S., & Leonard, A. (1993). Contributions to vortex particle methods for the computation of three-dimensional incompressible unsteady flows. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 109(2), 247-273.
- [20] Alvarez, E. J., & Ning, A. (2018). Development of a vortex particle code for the modeling of wake interaction in distributed propulsion. In *2018 Applied Aerodynamics Conference* (p. 3646), Atlanta, Georgia, US.
- [21] Farassat, F. (2007). Derivation of Formulations 1 and 1A of Farassat (No. L-19318).
- [22] Han, F., Lopes de Moraes Filho, L. F., Rezgui, D., Turhan, B., Azarpeyvand, M., Gautam, A., Zang B. & Zhou, B. Y. (2025). Aerodynamic Performance of Distributed Electric Propulsion Wing Under Different Design and Operating Parameters. In *AIAA AVIATION 2025 Forum*, Las Vegas, US.